

Subject:

Political Science

Title:

**Resolving the Assam-Arunachal Pradesh Boundary Dispute:
Historical Perspectives, Challenges, and the Path Forward**

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Abstract:

The boundary disputes between Assam and its neighbouring northeastern states, including Arunachal Pradesh, have caused significant tensions and violence over the decades. These disputes stem from the colonial era and intensified after the creation of states like Mizoram, Meghalaya, Arunachal Pradesh, and Nagaland from Assam. The Assam-Arunachal Pradesh dispute centres around the 1951 notification, which transferred 3,648 sq km of land to Assam, a decision strongly contested by Arunachal Pradesh. Despite ongoing efforts by both state and central governments, the issue persists. However, recent developments, with both state Chief Ministers and the central government showing a strong commitment to resolving the dispute, offer hope for a peaceful resolution. This study explores these recent efforts and seeks to identify potential solutions based on the current developments.

Keywords:

Boundary, developments, peaceful, solutions

Introduction

Boundaries play very important role in all aspect, because it marks the limits of a states' sovereignty (Adhikari, Sudepta, 2007).ⁱ The Assam-Arunachal Pradesh boundary dispute, which spans 804 km with over 1,200 disputed points, dates back to 1873 when the British introduced the inner-line regulation to separate the plains from the frontier hills. This area became the North-East Frontier Tracts in 1915 and later NEFA in 1954. The dispute escalated in the 1990s, with significant flare-ups. A pivotal moment occurred in 1951 when 3,648 sq. km of land in the Balipara and Sadiya foothills was transferred from Arunachal Pradesh to Assam's Darrang and Lakhimpur districts (Das Pushpita, 2021).ⁱⁱ Since 1987, Arunachal Pradesh has celebrated its statehood, but resentment has grown among those in the transferred areas, as they were not consulted. Arunachal leaders argue the transfer ignored tribal rights, while Assam claims the 1951 demarcation is legal. Assam has faced boundary disputes with all northeastern states formed from it, including Nagaland (1963), Meghalaya (Autonomous State in 1970, full state in 1972), and Arunachal Pradesh and Mizoram (both became Union Territories in 1972 and states in 1987).ⁱⁱⁱ None of the new States accepted the "constitutional boundary" (Samy, 2022)^{iv} that they said was dictated by the partisan administration of undivided Assam without consulting the tribal stakeholders. The dispute originates from claims that tribal chieftains traditionally controlled the disputed areas before Assam inherited "imaginary boundaries" drawn during British rule. A 1951 report by a sub-committee led by Assam's first Chief Minister, Gopinath Bordoloi, added complexity. Multiple attempts were made to demarcate the boundary between Assam and NEFA/Arunachal Pradesh between 1971 and 1974.^v To resolve the boundary dispute, a high-powered tripartite committee, comprising the Centre and the two states, was established in April 1979 to delineate the boundary based on Survey of India maps. By 1984, 489 km of the boundary north of the Brahmaputra River was demarcated. However, Arunachal Pradesh rejected the recommendations, asserting claims over areas transferred to Assam in 1951. In response, Assam approached the Supreme Court in 1989, accusing Arunachal Pradesh of encroachment.^{vi} In 2006, the Supreme Court appointed a local boundary commission, led by a retired judge, to address the dispute. The commission's September 2014 report recommended that Arunachal Pradesh regain some of the

areas transferred in 1951 and urged both states to engage in discussions to find a compromise. However, this recommendation was not implemented.

Recent development

Boundary disputes between Assam and Arunachal Pradesh remain pending in the Supreme Court, with progress stalled by states rejecting commission recommendations. For example, Assam rejected the 2014 report recommending the transfer of 70-80% of disputed land to Arunachal Pradesh. Consequently, both states' Chief Ministers have agreed to resolve the dispute outside the court. The proposal for the out-of-court settlement (Karmakar Sumir, 2021)^{vii} was made by Arunachal Pradesh's chief minister when his Assam counterpart had visited Arunachal to attend a road inauguration programme in kinim during 2021.^{viii} After the Union Home Minister's intervention, Arunachal Pradesh formed a high-powered ministerial committee on July 15, 2021, led by Bamang Felix. In January 2022, the Chief Ministers of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh met in Guwahati and agreed to conduct a ground-level survey of the boundary status.^{ix}

On Arunachal Pradesh's 36th statehood day, a collaborative, rational approach to resolving the Assam-Arunachal boundary dispute is emphasized. An integrated committee can streamline information sharing and resource planning, serving as a model for similar disputes. Assam must focus on rational solutions, economic growth, and effective communication. Assam Chief Minister Himanta Biswa Sarma assured Arunachal Pradesh of the government's readiness to resolve the dispute amicably. Following progress in the Assam-Meghalaya border dispute, both Chief Ministers agreed to form district-level committees, inspired by the positive Assam-Meghalaya agreement. The shared governance of both states under the BJP and the Centre's support is seen as crucial in expediting the resolution.^x

Mediation Efforts

Following the Assam-Meghalaya resolution model, Assam and Arunachal Pradesh have agreed to form district-level committees for joint surveys in disputed sectors, aiming to find tangible solutions to the long-pending issues.: -

- Historical perspective,
- Ethnicity
- Contiguity
- People's will
- Administrative convenience of both the States.

Renewed efforts, including political dialogues and MoUs, have focused on de-escalation. Assam and Arunachal Pradesh have engaged in discussions, with a 2023 agreement aiming to settle boundary issues. Both states will establish 12 committees, with Assam contributing eight districts and Arunachal Pradesh twelve, using satellite mapping for accurate demarcation. Reviving the Inter-State Council and Zonal Councils could facilitate resolution through policy coordination and discussions on shared concerns. Strengthening cooperative federalism is key to promoting India's unity in diversity.^{xi}

Analysis

The Rights and Risks Analysis Group (RRAG), an independent think tank, published a report titled '*Border Disputes in the North East: The Raging War Within*', recommending measures to maintain the status

quo until a final solution is reached, focusing on preventing human rights violations and upholding the rule of law and democracy: -

- I. Identify the de-facto control line and deploy coordinated police forces from both states under CRPF supervision to manage disputes and maintain law and order.
- II. Jointly maintain and enforce law and order along the de-facto control line.
- III. Conduct biometric documentation of residents in disputed areas, issue IDs, and publish names in the gazette to prevent new settlements without mutual agreement
- IV. Prohibit new settlements or structures in disputed areas and require mutual consent from both states for any activity, including police entry along the de-facto control line
- V. Ensure mutual consent from both the states for any activity including entry of the police along the line of de facto control.^{xii}

Given the complexity of the Assam-Arunachal Pradesh boundary dispute, the formation of an independent interstate boundary commission is crucial. The commission should propose solutions, such as compensating one state or dividing disputed land equally. Both states are committed to an out-of-court resolution. On June 1, 2022, Arunachal Pradesh formed 12 regional committees to examine the dispute, while Assam's governor established 12 committees for 123 border villages. These committees will coordinate with district-level teams, verify population data, and engage local communities, based on the 2010 Survey Report. The 123 villages is segregated in the following manner –

- Village falling in Arunachal Pradesh – 21
- Village falling in Assam – 15
- Village falling on both the side – 07
- Village which could not be located in the survey report – 80

So the 12 districts of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh which share boundary and are the bone of contention among them are as follows –

1. West Siang (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Udalgiri and Sonitpur (Assam).
2. Pakke Kessang (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Sonitpur and Biswanath (Assam).
3. Papumpare (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Biswanath and Lakhimpur (Assam).
4. Kamle (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Lakhimpur (Assam).
5. Lower Siang (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Dhemaji (Assam).
6. East Siang (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Dhemaji and Tinsukia (Assam).
7. Lower Dibang valley (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Tinsukia (Assam).
8. Lohit (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Tinsukia (Assam).
9. Namsai (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Tinsukia (Assam).
10. Changlang (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Tinsukia (Assam).
11. Tirap (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Tinsukia and Dibrugarh (Assam).
12. Longding (Arunachal Pradesh) borders Dibrugarh and Charaideo (Assam).

Measures

Following measures can be taken:

1. Making sure that local communities are heard during border resolution procedures by means of participatory decision-making and consultations.
2. Strengthening the judiciary's role in promoting a just and legally binding resolution through judicial and legal arbitration.
3. Increasing interstate coordination for economic cooperation, border security, and resource sharing is known as administrative cooperation.
4. Using communication and restitution to resolve historical injustices and acknowledge past grievances is known as historical reconciliation.

Conclusion

The Assam-Arunachal Pradesh boundary dispute requires a comprehensive and inclusive resolution. The ambiguity surrounding territorial boundaries in the Indian subcontinent stems from territorial claims by states and sub-state authorities, often disregarding the views of local communities, leading to regional violence. These disputes arise from the imposition of modern state borders over historical ones. While recent agreements show progress, a lasting solution requires a multi-stakeholder approach. By fostering dialogue, legal clarity, and administrative cooperation, Assam and Arunachal Pradesh can work towards peaceful coexistence and regional stability.

ⁱ Sudepta Adhikari, *Political Geography*, Rawat Publication, India, 2007, p.195.

ⁱⁱ Pushpita Das, *Inter-State border disputes in Northeast India*, MP-IDSA, 29th July 2021.

ⁱⁱⁱ Rahul Karmakar, *Towards a resolution of the Arunachal-Assam border dispute*, The Hindu, April 25, 2022 17:07 IST.

^{iv} Samy, *In the direction of a decision of the Arunachal-Assam border dispute*, Tech Oro, 25th April, 2022.

^v Dakter Esse, *A study of Assam-Arunachal Pradesh Border Narratives*, Ph.D. Thesis Department of Cultural studies, Tezpur University, 2017, P-73.

^{vi} Bhubaneswar Bhattacharyya, *The troubled border: Some facts about boundary disputes between Assam-Nagaland, Assam-Arunachal Pradesh, Assam-Meghalaya, and Assam-Mizoram*, Lawyer's Book Stall, P-205

^{vii} Sumir Karmakar, *Assam-Arunachal agree for out-of court settlement of long border dispute*, DHNS, July 15 2021, 21:59 IST.

^{viii} The Indian Express, *Disputed land should be returned to Arunachal, says panel report*, Feb. 1, 2014, 1:52:51 am.

^{ix} Business standard, *Assam-Arunachal border dispute likely to be resolved by next year*, 21 may, 2022, 17:42 IST PTI Deomali

^x Staff Reporter *Assam ready to do anything to resolve boundary dispute: Sarma*, The Arunachal Times Feb 22, 2022

^{xi} Tora Agarwala, *Assam, Arunachal Pradesh to form district-level committees to solve border dispute*, The Indian Express, April 20, 2022

^{xii} Subhas Chakma, *Border disputes in the Northeast: Durable peace is possible*, The Arunachal Times, August 8, 2021

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